

THE ROLE OF THE TRANSPORT SYSTEM IN THE ECONOMY

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Abstract: This thesis examines the role of the transport network in the national economy and issues of increasing its competitiveness. The impact of the transport system on economic growth, logistics efficiency, and international trade development is analyzed. Also, indicators for assessing competitiveness in the transport network and an integrated index-based approach are highlighted. The impact of modernization and digitalization of transport infrastructure on economic efficiency is substantiated.

Keywords: transport system, competitiveness, logistics, economic efficiency, transport infrastructure.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследуется роль транспортной сети в национальной экономике и вопросы повышения ее конкурентоспособности. Анализируется влияние транспортной системы на экономический рост, эффективность логистики и развитие международной торговли. Также рассматриваются показатели оценки конкурентоспособности транспортной сети и интегрированный индексный подход. Обосновывается влияние модернизации и цифровизации транспортной инфраструктуры на экономическую эффективность.

Ключевые слова: транспортная система, конкурентоспособность, логистика, экономическая эффективность, транспортная инфраструктура.

The transport system is an infrastructure sector of strategic importance for the economy of each country. It not only ensures the timely delivery of products, raw materials and services, but also connects various sectors of economic activity, increasing the country's competitiveness. World experience shows that the effective functioning of

the transport system plays an important role in economic growth, expanding export potential and strengthening international trade relations.

The operation of the transport system has a significant impact not only on the global competitiveness of the goods market, but also on the growth and development of other service and public service sectors. The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-329 of October 10, 2023 on the reform of the railway transport sector in 2023–2026 sets out priority tasks aimed at reforming the railway transport sector, creating a healthy competitive environment, widely involving the private sector in the sector, digitizing business processes, introducing modern management methods, and effectively using the transit potential of the republic.

In the context of the globalized processes that encompass the world economy and related supply chains and interregional relations, the importance of transport infrastructure is constantly increasing. In particular, according to analytical data on the main indicators of 2024, based on the report on the work carried out by the Ministry of Transport on the results of 2024, the positive growth dynamics in the transport sector of our country was maintained. In particular, 114 trillion 553.3 billion soums of transport services were provided (108.6 percent compared to 2023).

For information: 57.1 trillion soums (112.4%) were provided in road transport, 10.42 trillion soums (99%) in railway transport, and 16.6 trillion soums (102%) in air transport. The share of transport services in total services was 17.6%. Also, 1 billion 455.7 million tons of cargo were transported (102.4% compared to 2023). For information: 70 million tons (95%) were transported by rail, 14.6 thousand tons (101%) by air, and 1 billion 326 million tons (101%) by road.

1st cm . Strategic objectives of the development of¹the transportation system in the country

The presented figure 1 reflects the strategic goals of developing the transport system in the country. It focuses on the main aspects that can have a significant impact on economic development, the social sphere and international relations:

- The main directions of development of the transport system are the equal development of all regions, increasing population mobility indicators and reducing transport costs.

¹Author's development based on sources

- Ensuring the competitiveness of enterprises by reducing logistics costs. To this end, it is necessary to optimize transport routes, introduce modern transport management technologies, and develop multimodal transport;

- As a result of the development of logistics infrastructure, it is possible to reduce the delivery time of goods, increase the efficiency of logistics processes, and create a unified information system for the construction of logistics centers and transport management;

- To improve the business environment, attract investment, and increase exports by developing transport infrastructure and creating a favorable investment climate to increase the competitiveness of the economy

- Reducing unemployment and increasing incomes by creating new jobs. This includes developing the transport sector and establishing new enterprises

- Improving the transport capabilities of tourist facilities and creating a modern tourist infrastructure to attract tourists and increase income from tourism as a result of the development of tourism industries introduce modern technologies for managing the transport system and optimize routes in order to reduce transport costs and improve the quality of services

- Support the development of small and medium-sized businesses and open up opportunities for creating new jobs

- Creating a favorable investment climate and paving the way for the promotion of investment projects by financing infrastructure projects and developing the economy through attracting investments

- The strategic goals are to increase exports and imports due to the growth of foreign economic relations, as well as to develop transport infrastructure and simplify customs procedures through integration into world economic processes.

It is appropriate to consider the impact of infrastructure on economic development not only in terms of quantitative growth, but also in terms of qualitative changes in the economy, that is, the impact on the spread of scientific and technological progress and innovations. The transport system is revealed through the specific results of its impact on the socio-economic development of the country (Table1).

The transport system plays an important strategic role in the country's economic development. It is one of the main tools for strengthening international and regional integration, and the effective use of transit potential contributes to an increase in international trade, expansion of export opportunities and an increase in foreign exchange earnings. The development of modern transport routes reduces product delivery times and costs, which increases the efficiency of the production and trade sectors, reduces the cost of products and strengthens competitiveness. Transport infrastructure also has a positive impact on regional development. It reduces economic and social disparities between internal regions and increases the ability to attract investment.

New jobs are created through transport projects, including during the construction of roads, railways and ports, and the expansion of the transport sector increases employment in the service sector. The efficient supply of industrial and agricultural products to domestic and foreign markets supports the sustainable development of these sectors. The smooth operation of the logistics system ensures the successful operation of exporting companies. The transport system also directly affects the development of tourism. Convenient and fast transport services increase the flow of tourists, leading to the growth of hotels, restaurants and other industries.

Table 1

The secret of the national economic development of the transport network ¹.

T/r	Type of exposure	The consequences of the impact
1.	Directly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - decrease/increase in the cost of production of the product; - decrease / increase in the efficiency of local enterprises; - population mobility, recreational opportunities, and growth/restriction of social connections; - expansion / restriction of interregional relations.
2.	Indirectly	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - growth in regional agricultural production ; - aligning the development of the regions ; - improve the investment climate ; - Increasing innovation activity . - promoting the intensive development of related industries ; - increasing the efficiency of using other production factors , increasing market opportunities for using them ; - Formation of aggregate demand.
3.	Deadline	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Long - term improvement : business and Satisfy the needs of the population for high - quality transport services ; increase tax revenues due to the availability of transport infrastructure ; provide the population with jobs ; create jobs ; provide the population with products (supply) . - Short - term effect : increase in interest rates or , on the contrary , increase in interest rates ; to meet the needs of

		the state to move to different countries at a certain time of the year
4.	According to the display medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Endogenous secret : business To improve transport connections ; to increase the investment attractiveness of the region and its quality as a permanent residence . - Exogenous influence : the addition of mint aqa to the economic relations of the mint aqal .
5.	Depending on the level of impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Local level - development of internal trade , expansion of local markets , increase in business opportunities , increase in population mobility . - Regional development - expansion of business , increasing opportunities for forming agglomerations ; It is important to know the state of affairs and the company 's staff . - National level - ensuring national security , territorial integrity of the country , creating opportunities for expanding business , and the availability of capital .

the transport infrastructure allows for increased economic efficiency and environmental safety. At the same time, the transport system is an important factor in meeting the social needs of the population. It expands access to healthcare, education and other services, increases people's mobility and saves time. In countries with a geographically favorable location, the transport system becomes an additional source of income through the development of transit corridors, and an increase in the volume of international cargo transportation brings significant income to the national economy. The effective functioning of the transport system ensures the interconnectedness of trade, production and service sectors and supports the consistent continuation of

economic growth. Therefore, the transport system is of strategic importance for the country's economic development, and supporting its innovative development and increasing its efficiency is an important task.

Today, the processes of global economic integration, the increase in the volume of investments in transport infrastructure and the interrelation between the geographical location of facilities have made the competitiveness of transport networks an important object of research. Competitiveness is important not only for the national economy, but also for local regional development. After all, an efficient transport system ensures the timely and affordable delivery of goods and services, which stimulates business activity, expands foreign trade opportunities and improves the quality of life of the population.

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